

This project has received funding
from the European Union's Horizon
2020 research and innovation
programme under grant agreement
No 776816

project

D7.2: Users collaborative platform. Platform's requirements and specifications

V.2 – 05.2020

Status of deliverable: PUBLIC

Main authors: Exergy, revision by FPM

Deliverable Review and Approval

The individuals listed below are not directly involved in the preparation of this deliverable and will review the present document.

Name	Organization
	Exergy

Deliverable Development and Review Process

	Key Event	Deadline	Done by
1	Submission of Draft Deliverable to reviewers	02/09/2019	Exergy
2	Initial Review and Comments obtained	16/09/2019	Exergy
3	Uploading and submission of Final Deliverable on Participant Portal	30/09/2019	Exergy
4	Revision	25/05/2020	FPM

Executive summary

This document presents an approach to the identification of the roles, profiles and requirements for the development of Project O platform. The document includes the definition of the user roles, an in-depth study of the needs and requirements of the participants from the point of view of user stories, and the subsequent definition of product functions to solve the identified requirements.

In Task 7.2, Exergy will develop a system toolbox by website and/or application which will be used for the organisations to implement their new circular business models. This report describes the preliminary requirements to implement a common front end that allows the user interaction with different microservices, an integrated marketplace for water resources and related services, and communication tools for the key actors involved.

The Users Collaborative Platform will implement strategies related to treating, reusing, recycling and recovering water, resources and energy, to encourage the stakeholders to engage with the circular economy principles. It would also integrate the different user profiles involved within Project Ô, allowing them the access to information generated through the different tools. For instance, it will connect water users and technology providers through the information of products and performance. This platform would basically expose and allow the access to resources and services of the different stakeholders through a unified web frontend.

The Users Collaborative Platform would be implemented as a web platform to encourage the circularity of resources, principally water, energy and by-products derived from water treatment. It revolves around the interaction of two perspectives, one that requests for products and services within the circularity purpose and another perspective that supplies those products or services.

All information and data used by the platform will be processed in compliance with the contents of the Data Management Plan of Project Ô (D 1.2-6).

Table of Contents

Deliverable Review and Approval.....	1
Deliverable Development and Review Process.....	1
Executive summary.....	2
Table of Contents	3
1. Introduction.....	4
1.1. Description of the document and purpose.....	4
1.2. WPs and Tasks related with the deliverable.....	4
2. Users Collaborative Platform.....	5
3. General description of the platform	5
1. Value chain and high level requirements	6
2. User stories	8
1. Potential user 1:.....	9
2. Potential user 2.....	10
3. Potential user 3.....	11
4. Potential user 4.....	12
5. Potential user 5.....	13
6. Potential user 6.....	13
7. Potential user 6.....	14
8. Potential user 7.....	15
4. Platform functionalities and requirement catalogue	16
2. AssignCollection.....	20
3. AssignDelivery.....	20
4. Authenticate	20
5. deleteResources	21
6. ManageLogistics	21
7. manageResource	21
8. Register	21
9. RequestResource	22
10. UpdateResource	22
5. Conclusions.....	24
6. Appendix A	25

1. Introduction

The main objective of Project Ô is to demonstrate approaches and technologies to drive an integrated and symbiotic use of water contributing to the transition towards a circular economy, addressing technical, economic, environmental and social aspects to redefine value chains.

Project Ô aims at implementing circular economy models for water and used water management systems, with high potential of cross-sectorial replicability and transferability by directly addressing and demonstrating key stages along the entire circular setup. It addresses the different stages of the water management value chain, with special focus on new/improved water treatment technologies development, circular business models definition, user platforms and water management streams.

The stakeholder platform would allow the different actors of the value chain to share information (e.g. water and resources streams, resource characteristics, use patterns, etc) and services through a unified web frontend. The platform will implement strategies to foster the circularity by promoting local closed loops.

1.1. Description of the document and purpose

In Task 7.2, Exergy will develop a system toolbox by website and/or application which will be used for the organisations to implement their new circular business models. This report describes the preliminary requirements to implement a common front end that allows the user interaction with different microservices, an integrated marketplace for water resources and related services, and communication tools for the key actors involved.

1.2. WPs and Tasks related with the deliverable

The User Collaborative Platform is part of the WP7 Circularity of water and circular economy: interfacing systemic issues with innovative business models. This WP issues the decision-making platform for water (and water technologies) users, to assess business impacts of innovative, small loops of water management and opportunities for circular economy. It groups a set of tools and business models to enable interaction between the actors, the databases to store information, and the capabilities to analysing/processing that information. Figure 1 presents the interdependencies between the work packages of the project, where it can be observed the different flows of information (performance data, stakeholders needs and results) in WP7.

All relevant information, like economic baseline, energy prices, labour prices, scenarios of future availability and requests for the supply of resources, defined in the Project, will provide the context information to support user choices.

The procedures will be implemented in the platform relating to data collection, storage, access, sharing policies, protection, retention and destruction will be compliant with the Regulation (EU) 2016/679 and EU standards, as specified in the Data Management Plan of Project Ô (yearly updating D 1.2, D1.3, D1.4, D1.5 and final version D1.6).

Figure 1 - Work packages interdependencies

2. Users Collaborative Platform

The Users Collaborative Platform will implement strategies related to treating, reusing, recycling and recovering water, resources and energy, to encourage the stakeholders to engage with the circular economy principles. It would also integrate the different user profiles involved within Project Ô, allowing them the access to information generated through the different tools. For instance, it will connect water users and technology providers through the information of products and performance. This platform would basically expose and allow the access to resources and services of the different stakeholders through a unified web frontend.

The platform will be developed adopting a modular approach (see also Section 4) and relying on open source technologies in order to obtain more robust and general-use software components. This architecture will also help to extend the life of the platform and of its modules after the end of the project. The legacy of the platform will be considered and detailed in the deliverable D7.3, analysing the possibility of using it as basis for the development of a commercial product.

3. General description of the platform

The Users Collaborative Platform would be implemented as a web platform to encourage the circularity of resources, principally water, and secondly energy and by-products derived from water treatment. It revolves around the interaction of two perspectives, one that requests for products and services within the circularity purpose and another perspective that supplies those products or services.

The user could request a water quantity either to buy it or to receive it without cost (e.g. a user requesting for water containing fertilizers). Additionally, the user might be interested on requesting a service associated to a

good she/he already owns. The user might be interested on treating water to extend its life cycle by continuing to use it in similar or other purposes (reuse/recycle); or disposing the water such that other person can make use of it in its current status, use it after treatment, or benefit from the by-products produced in the treatment process. In the supply/provide perspective, the user can provide a product, either selling it or giving it away. Additionally, in this perspective the user can provide a service such as maintenance, treatment, re-use and recycling. There are some complementary services that support the interaction within the request and supply perspectives, which are, for instance, Water management advice and logistics support such as transport and distribution.

Figure 2 - General overview of the Users Collaborative Platform

The app will be modular, which means that different modules are going to be integrated. Each of these modules will give an answer for a specific interaction between stakeholders within the framework of the relation of the two perspectives (request-supply). Likewise, the proposed approach allows the platform to be developed by the different microservices and thus providing opportunities for future modules/functionalities to be implemented. Platform requirements

1. Value chain and high level requirements

The preliminary requirements for the platform were defined through the analysis of the circular value chain envisioned to promote closed loops in two of the demonstrators, namely, Eilat in Israel and Omis WTPP in Croatia. The analysis of the value chain for the different demosites was reported in D7.6: Creation of a circular economy framework for water treatment with the inclusion of energy and materials. The identify value chains are shown in Figure 3 and Figure 4.

Figure 3 - Project O value chain for Eilat demo

Figure 4 - Project O value chain for Omis WTPP demo

The platform to be piloted will integrate the functionalities of a marketplace with additional functionalities to promote circular principles fostering resources, products and material life extension. Moreover, the platform aims at empowering end-users and provide communication with main stakeholders in the value chain:

Support the decision-making process to circulate and/or dispose resource streams, products and materials based on a decision support system

Provide on the same tool the possibility to arrange the logistic for products collection/delivery by integrating local courier and emerging decentralised initiative (Van and a Man)

Direct communication with stakeholder along the value chain to promote local and wider collaboration in industrial symbiosis

In particular, the end-user platform will empower the final end-user and will allow them to obtain or circulate products resources and products. Therefore, in the proposed scope, it is in principle the final-end user supported by the Decision Support System (DSS) who makes the decision about the best option to obtain, circulate or dispose resource streams (e.g. water streams) and products. All relevant information, like economic baseline, energy prices, labour prices, scenarios of future availability and requests for the supply of resources, collected and/or produced in the Project, will provide the context information to support user choices. The platform will be designed to allow the aggregation of information from different marketplaces, if available, relevant to the local market, and accessible from a legal point of view.

In order to facilitate the end-user decision, the platform would present them with a set of alternatives engaging other end-users, facility managers, retailers, collectors, waste managers, among other key actors. In its more basic approach the platform will provide the following functionalities:

Get/buy. The user that wants to get a specific resource or product should be able to see the adds that other users have posted in Project O marketplace. In order to do so, there will be a search bar in which the

user specifies the item she/he is looking for. A list of coincidences is then showed. The list is also available to be seen on a map that geolocates the adds that match the search query. Additionally, there is a browsing option for the user to see all the ads near a specific location.

Give away/sell. The user that wants to sell or give away a resource or product would be presented a form to provide the basic information of the item to sell or give away. The information will be shown as an advert and depicted on a map.

Collection service for energy recovery of final dispose. This functionality will provide user with information of collection services and EoL strategies for resources and products when options for other loops are not available.

2. User stories

An initial step to define the scope and target users for the platform, is profiling the most relevant users. Each of those users was associated with a 'persona' for which a brief profile was created describing the main singularities of the user. The outcomes that each 'persona' could expect from the platform were also listed to be validated with actual end-users. The interaction process was then described as a set of users liked to specific functionalities.

In the next deliverable "Description and details of the Users Collaborative Platform" (D7.3), the user stories will be extended and more focalized on the demosites needs, taking advantage of the information collected and interaction with the partners responsible for specific implementations.

A generic user story for the platform was defined considering the demo activities in Eilat and Croatia

1. An organization is interesting in identifying the best options to manage different resource stream (e.g. Water effluent) from their industrial process. The user interacts with the platform to either identify options to circulate and manage a resource coming out from their process or to identify resources from other industries that they could integrate in their process
 - a. In the former scenario in which the user is looking to circulate or dispose an item, the user will interact with the platform to identify potential routes to allow those actions. Those routes could include treatment technologies, internal and external valorisation in others industrial processes or product, final disposal, among others.
 - b. in the latter case, the user experience will relate to the experience of a marketplace but would extend beyond the product browsing and search to support the logistic arrangements and interactions with other stakeholders.
2. Once from the end user is registered, a decision support algorithm will allow to identify alternatives to be presented
3. The decision support system will interact with the logistic platform to provide a first estimation of costs, time an environmental impact of the alternatives
4. The platform will present the alternatives to the user and ask whether support for collection and delivery is needed.
5. The platform will interact with the database to identify options for service providers which could cover treatments, collection, final disposal, among others.
6. The user would be then matched with the actors involved in the action decided to pursue.
- 7.
- 8.

The focus of the platform for the Project will covered mainly the following actors and stakeholders:

- 1) Water intensive business

- 2) Wastewater producers and water users
- 3) Facility managers
- 4) Technology manufacturers
- 5) Local authorities
- 6) Logistic operators

The requirements for platform were compiled using detailed user stories, which define the needs of end-users and stakeholders using the end-user platform. An example of the approach adopted is presented below for the Facility managers. The detail user stories are presented in the Appendix A.

1. Potential user 1:

User: Water intensive business

Profile:

- Interested in reusing and/or recycling wastewater
- Basic knowledge on water treatment technologies but not the options available
- Willing to implement water treatment system for reuse in own business processes
- Willing to implement water treatment system for recycling and sell/give away to other businesses
- Willing to sell used water to other businesses
- Interested in higher energy efficiency of technologies
- Limited environmental concern, mostly economic driven
- Financially strong, could consider upfront costs if ROI is adequate

Expected outcomes:

- Greater understanding of the water treatment available options
- Decision support on what technology or treatment process best fits the purpose
- Information about potential recycled water buyers or partnerships
- Financial savings from
 - water disposal reduction
 - fresh water supply demand reduction
 - benefits from recycled water sale
- Energy savings from energy efficient technology
- Financial projections
- Potential by-products to be obtained

Interaction process:

- Found the tool through search engine or advert (Web platform)
- Account and profile creation
- Input basic information from the activities (business activity, location, looking for selling/giving away and reusing/recycling resources, type of resource: water, energy, materials, by-products)
 - Selling: water process type, water output flow, water output quality,
 - Reusing: water output flow, water output quality, desired water input flow, water input quality, output water process type, input water process type.

- Define criteria for selection (cost savings, environment, energy savings, resource savings, performance)
- Access basic results (potential used water and treated water buyers, their location and required input water flow and quality, water treatment technology options, technology cost, installation costs, fuel costs, maintenance cost, performance, energy savings, financial incentives if any, environmental benefits, potential by-products obtained from treatment)
- Based on preferences, get a shortlist of technology options
- Select the most relevant technologies
- Provide further information about technologies (links from database)
 - Technology quotes
 - Contact of potential installers, geographical representation, preliminary quotes
 - Technology purchase through UCP
 - Best water buyer match based on proximity and water quality and flow target
 - Potential market, buyers or uses of by-products obtained in treatment

2. Potential user 2

User: Start-up, water producer, environmentally-friendly

Profile:

- Interested in reusing and/or recycling wastewater
- Intermediate knowledge on water treatment technologies and some options available
- Willing to implement water treatment system for reuse in own business processes
- Willing to implement water treatment system for recycling and sell to other businesses
- Interested in higher energy efficiency of technologies
- Strong environmental concern
- Financially weak, not able to consider medium-low upfront costs

Expected outcomes:

- Greater understanding of the water treatment available options
- Decision on what technology or treatment process best fits the purpose
- Information about potential recycled water buyers
- Financial savings from water disposal reduction
- Financial savings from reducing fresh water supply demand
- Financial benefits from recycled water sale
- Energy savings from energy efficient technology
- Financial projections

Interaction process:

- Found the tool through search engine or advert (phone app or web platform)
- Account and profile creation
- Input basic information from the activities (business activity, location, looking for selling/giving away and reusing/recycling resources, type of resource: water, energy, materials, by-products)
 - Selling: water process type, water output flow, water output quality,
 - Reusing: water output flow, water output quality, desired water input flow, water input quality, output water process type, input water process type.
- Define criteria for selection (economy, environment, energy savings, resource savings, performance)

- Access basic results (potential used water and treated water buyers, their location and required input water flow and quality, water treatment technology options, technology cost, installation costs, fuel costs, maintenance cost, performance, energy savings, financial incentives if any, environmental benefits, potential by-products obtained from treatment)
- Based on preferences, get a shortlist of technology options
- Select the most relevant technologies
- Provide further information about technologies (links from database)
 - Technology quotes
 - Contact of potential installers, geographical representation, preliminary quotes
 - Technology purchase through UCP
 - Best water buyer match based on proximity and water quality and flow target
 - Potential market, buyers or uses of by-products obtained in treatment

3. Potential user 3

User: Start-up, water consumer, environmentally-friendly

Profile:

- Interested in reusing wastewater from water intensive producers
- Basic knowledge on water treatment technologies and options available
- Willing to buy used water, implement water treatment system and use treated water in their processes
- Willing to buy treated water and using it in their processes
- Strong environmental concern
- Financially weak, consider medium-low upfront costs

Expected outcomes:

- Greater understanding of the water treatment available options
- Decision on what technology or treatment process best fits the purpose
- Information about potential recycled water sellers
- Financial savings from cheaper water supply cost
- Environmental benefits for reduction in fresh water demand
- Information about payback periods for the different water treatment options
- Financial projections

Interaction process:

- Found the tool through search engine or advert (phone app or web platform)
- Account and profile creation
- Input basic information from the activities (business activity, location, looking for buying/acquiring resources, type of resource: water, energy, materials, by-products)
 - Buying: water process type, desired water input flow, water input quality,
- Define criteria for selection (economy, environment, energy savings, resource savings, performance)
- Access basic results (potential used water and treated water sellers, their location and output water flow and quality, water treatment technology options, technology cost, installation costs, fuel costs, maintenance cost, performance, financial incentives if any, environmental benefits, potential by-products obtained from treatment)
- Based on preferences, get a shortlist of technology options

- Select the most relevant technologies
- Provide further information about technologies (links from database)
 - Technology quotes
 - Contact of potential installers, geographical representation, preliminary quotes
 - Technology purchase through UCP
 - Best water seller match based on proximity and water quality and flow target
 - Potential market, buyers or uses of by-products obtained in treatment

4. Potential user 4

User: Farmer

Profile:

- Interested in reusing wastewater from water intensive producers if meets required quality
- No knowledge on water treatment technologies and options available
- Willing to buy treated water and using it in their processes
- Financially weak, consider medium-low upfront costs
- Medium environmental concern
- Consider buying treatment technologies if significant cost savings or useful by-products are obtained

Expected outcomes:

- Information about potential recycled water sellers
- Financial savings from cheaper water supply cost
- Environmental benefits for reduction in fresh water demand
- Financial projections
- Information about potential by-product sellers, fertilizers, from treated water
- Information on technologies or treatment process available that best fit the purpose
- Information on payback period of treatment system

Interaction process:

- Found the tool through search engine or advert (web platform)
- Account and profile creation
- Input basic information from the activities (business activity, location, looking for buying/acquiring resources, type of resource: water, energy, materials, by-products)
 - Buying: water process type, desired water input flow, water input quality,
- Define criteria for selection (economy, environment, energy savings, resource savings, performance)
- Access basic results (potential used water and treated water sellers, their location and output water flow and quality, water treatment technology options, technology cost, installation costs, fuel costs, maintenance cost, performance, financial incentives if any, environmental benefits, potential by-products obtained from treatment)
- Based on preferences, get a shortlist of technology options
- Select the most relevant technologies
- Provide further information about technologies (links from database)
 - Technology quotes
 - Contact of potential installers, geographical representation, preliminary quotes
 - Technology purchase through UCP
 - Best water seller match based on proximity and water quality and flow target

- Best by-product seller match based on proximity and water quality and flow target
- Potential market, buyers or uses of by-products obtained in treatment

5. Potential user 5

User: Technology manufacturer

Profile:

- Interested in connecting waste water producers and users
- Expert knowledge on water treatment technologies and options available
- Willing to sell their technologies as product
- Willing to offer their technologies as services (rental)
- Financially strong, consider high upfront costs
- Limited environmental concern, mostly economic driven

Expected outcomes:

- Information about potential used or recycled water sellers and buyers
- Information about water quality and flow to be treated and also supplied
- Knowledge concerning potential by-product obtention from treated water
- Environmental benefits for reduction in fresh water demand and disposal
- Financial projections
- Information on payback period of treatment system to be used as marketing strategy

Interaction process:

- Found the tool through search engine or advert (web platform)
- Account and profile creation
- Input basic information from the products offered (type of treatment technology, stage in the treatment process, type of pollutants treated, sizes and flow range, performance, technology cost, installation costs, energy consumption, fuel type, O&M costs)
- Access basic results (potential used water and treated water sellers, their location and output water flow and quality, environmental benefits, potential by-products obtained from treatment)
- Based on preferences, recommendations shortlist
 - Best water seller and buyer match based on proximity and water quality and flow target
 - Suggested technology from manufacturer that fits best the purpose described
 - Best by-product seller match based on proximity and water quality and flow target
 - Potential market, buyers or uses of by-products obtained in treatment

6. Potential user 6

User: Water utility manager

Profile:

- Interested in connecting waste water producers and users for reducing water waste
- Committed about reducing the pressure into the water treatment plants
- Advanced knowledge on water treatment technologies and options available
- Financially strong, consider high upfront costs
- Strong environmental concern

Expected outcomes:

- Information about potential used or recycled water sellers and buyers
- Information about water quality and flow to be treated and also supplied
- Environmental benefits for reduction in fresh water demand and disposal
- Financial projections
- Information on payback period of treatment system
- Resource savings (water and energy)

Interaction process:

- Found the tool through search engine or advert (web platform)
- Account and profile creation
- Input basic information from the activities (business activity, location, looking to manage water flows)
- Access basic results (potential used water and treated water sellers and buyers, their location and output water flow and quality, water savings, cost savings, environmental benefits, future potential infrastructure projections to connect industrial areas)
- Based on preferences, recommendations shortlist
 - Best water seller and buyer match based on proximity and water quality and flow target
 - Water savings, relief of utilities and water treatment plant pressure
 - Cost savings in terms of energy consumption reduction due to less amount of water to be circulated and treated

7. Potential user 6

User: Off-grid/rural community

- Interested in reusing wastewater from nearby industries
- No knowledge on water treatment technologies and options available
- Willing to buy treated water and using it in their processes
- Financially weak, consider medium-low upfront costs
- Limited environmental concern
- Consider buying treatment technologies if significant cost savings or useful by-products are obtained

Expected outcomes:

- Information about nearby water producers
- Knowledge about future water infrastructure developments
- Information on technologies or treatment process available that best fit the purpose

Interaction process:

- Found the tool through search engine or advert (web platform)
- Account and profile creation
- Input basic information from the activities (business activity, location, looking for buying/acquiring resources, type of resource: water, energy, materials, by-products)
 - Buying: water process type, desired water input flow, water input quality,
- Define criteria for selection (economy, environment, energy savings, resource savings, performance)
- Access basic results (potential used water and treated water sellers, their location and output water flow and quality, water treatment technology options, technology cost, installation costs, fuel costs,

maintenance cost, performance, financial incentives if any, environmental benefits, potential by-products obtained from treatment)

- Based on preferences, get a shortlist of technology options
- Select the most relevant technologies
- Provide further information about technologies (links from database)
 - Technology quotes
 - Contact of potential installers, geographical representation, preliminary quotes
 - Technology purchase through UCP
 - Best water seller match based on proximity and water quality and flow target
 - Best by-product seller match based on proximity and water quality and flow target
 - Potential market, buyers or uses of by-products obtained in treatment

8. Potential user 7

User: Municipality

Profile:

- Interested in connecting waste water producers and users for reducing water waste
- Committed about reducing the pressure into the water treatment plants
- Medium knowledge on water treatment technologies and options available
- Financially strong, consider high upfront costs
- Strong environmental and social concern
- Defines the urban development plan, including future water infrastructure developments

Expected outcomes:

- Information about potential used or recycled water sellers and buyers
- Information about water quality and flow to be treated and also supplied
- Greater understanding of the water treatment available options
- Decision on what technology or treatment process best fits the purpose
- Environmental benefits for reduction in fresh water demand and disposal
- Financial and environmental savings from water disposal reduction
- Financial and environmental savings from reducing fresh water supply demand
- Financial projections
- Energy savings from energy efficient technology
- Information on payback period of treatment system
- Resource savings (water and energy)

Interaction process:

- Found the tool through search engine or advert (web platform)
- Account and profile creation
- Input basic information from the activities (business activity, location, looking to manage water flows)
- Access basic results (potential used water and treated water users and producers, their location and output water flow and quality, water savings, cost savings, environmental benefits, future potential infrastructure projections to connect industrial areas)
- Based on preferences, recommendations shortlist
 - Best water seller and buyer match based on proximity and water quality and flow target
 - Water savings, relief of utilities and water treatment plant pressure

- Cost savings in terms of energy consumption reduction due to less amount of water to be circulated and treated

4. Platform functionalities and requirement catalogue

Based on the previous developed user stories the following modules are foreseeing to be implemented:

- Sign in module. It would ask basic information of the user to create an account. The users are going to be classified either as natural persons or companies. The companies would need to provide additional information regarding their niche of business (e.g. water utilities, technology providers, water intensive companies, transport company, etc). The platform would be accessible without an initial registration to allow potential users to interact with the functionalities, however a registration form will be prompted before being able to complete transactions. It will be possible to sign in by automatically gathering the information from a linked Facebook, Gmail or Instagram account.
- Database module. This module aims at providing a single architecture for the data to be stored and accessible from the different functional modules. The database will compile data from different instances and among it the data to enable:
 - The effective implementation of modules fostering industrial symbiosis, B2B and C2B trading, and water reuse. That data would include technical information about water source and characteristics as well as target outcomes and KPIs; economic and environmental information for assessment of valorisation routes; user profiles and preferences; and requirements for logistic among others.
 - The implementation of the Technology Selection toolbox: Information from the technology manufacturers regarding technical, economic and environmental data of their products allowing for technology browsing, selection and optimization
- Trading module. It allows the users to trade resources. Three preliminary main use cases have been identified.
 - First, a user that wants to acquire resources (denoted get) either by buying them or getting them from someone that is giving the desired resource away.
 - Second, a user that wants to give away or dispose resources (denoted give). The trading is characterised by the fact that the ownership of the traded product changes moving from the user that gives the resource to the user that gets the resource.
 - Both user cases, get and give, can imply interactions between persons (C2C), persons and companies (C2B, B2C) and companies (B2B).

The modules will provide resource exchange opportunities and potential partnerships at a local/regional level.

Get/buy resources (C2C)

The user that wants to buy or get resources should be able to see the adds that other users have posted. In order to do so, there must be a search bar in which the user specifies the item she/he is looking for. A list of coincidences is then showed. The list is also available to be seen on a map that geolocates the adds that match the search query. Additionally, there is a browsing option for the user to see all the ads near a specific location.

Give away/sell resources (C2C)

The user that wants to sell or give away resources would be presented a form to provide the basic information of the resources to sell or give away. This information will be shown as an advert and depicted on the map. A search engine will look for companies that are interested in a specific type resource. Results are shown both in a list and geolocated in a map. Potential matches will be notified to the user creating the advert.

Sharing module

This module allows the users and companies to offer resources as a service paradigm.

- Sharing C2C. Two users would be able to agree the sharing/renting of resources or assets to treat and valorise their water streams.
- Sharing B2C. It allows a company to set a service to rent technologies or assets and offer them to the users looking for alternatives to treat and valorise their water streams without having to setup an in-house treatment capabilities. Filters to facilitate the search and renting and payments services will be available. T
- Treatment module. It allows the user to extend the life cycle of water by facilitating the interaction with the companies that provide treatment technologies so that instead of disposing the water, it can be treated and continuing in use either in internal or external loops. It implies interactions between users and technology providers or manufacturers (B2C). Circular business models approaches will be also considered identify potential situations where technology lease agreements or technology sharing schemes could be considered.
The module will be used mainly by facility manager, water treatment facilities and water system managers for the identification of the best technology solution and/or system of solutions to treat a specific water stream. It will also empower small communities and SMEs to implement virtuous practices for on-site circular use (or re-use) of water. The toolbox will provide technical, economic, environmental and regulatory information reported in a graphical way that enables the comparison between alternatives and facilitates their final decision.
The different treatment alternatives will be presented in a dashboard making available to the end user clear and compiled information about the economics, and the technical and environmental performance of the different technologies.
- Decision support system. This module will provide users with best alternatives and solutions to their needs. In the foreseen version to be developed in the framework of the project, the module would be based on a multicriteria decision models that could evolve to integrate other data analytic tools in future developments. The principal aim of MCDM is to help users synthesize the information so that they feel comfortable and confident about making a decision. MCDM integrates objective measurements with value judgments considering technical, environment and economic factors and makes explicit subjectivity.
This module will run a geographic information system (GIS) as a framework for gathering, managing, and analysing geographical data. It will make use of the internal coordinate system of a map or aerial photo image so it can be related to a ground system of geographic coordinates (such as latitude/longitude or UTM coordinates). Every platform user will be requested to input their business activities location, so that the module can display their geographical information in the internal map. This aspect will facilitate the suitability evaluation of resource exchange and partnerships though spacial analysis, proximity and capability, lending new perspectives to insights and decision-making

- Logistics module. The main logistics issues for the trading options and for the implementation of treatment process by technology deployment of technology as a service will be addressed in the platform. The main goal is to provide users with a one-stop shop concept that allows them to get in direct contact with technology providers and/or logistic operators, thus providing a one-stop-shop solution.

Likewise, among the main functionalities, the platform will allow to manage the users, access to the services and contents by integrating:

- Authentication: The platform involves a shared user data base that implements a Cross-Domain Single sign-on (CDSSO) mechanism for transferring user credentials across multiple secure domains. Therefore, the management and control of user credentials would be centralised.
- User Role information Additional information about the user is required to detail the users profile and be able to redirect the traffic to the different linked services. This information would be part of the centralised user information management in order to avoid duplicity and to be able to define access rules for the different services.
- Redirect traffic to exposed services: The platform would act as a gateway to expose the services and, based on the authentication procedures, it would redirect the user to the services they are granted access to.
- Service usage analytics: The platform would involve functionalities to track the activity of the users and analyse the usage patterns.
- Content provider: The platform would act as a portal in which news and calls about Circular Economy trends and the specific domains of the services exposed.

A preliminary requirement catalogue was built clustering the main functionalities foreseen to be implemented in the platform:

	Name	Primary Actors
	addResource	WaterStreamProducer
	AssignCollection	WaterStreamProducer, Technology provider, water user, logistic operator
	AssignDelivery	WaterStreamProducer, Technology provider, logistic operator
	authenticate	
	deleteResource	WaterStreamProducer
	manageLogistics	WaterStreamProducer, Technology provider, water user, logistic operator
	manageResource	WaterStreamProducer
	register	
	requestResource	water user
	updateResource	WaterStreamProducer
	viewResource	Technology provider, water user, logistic operator
	viewMarketPlace	WaterStreamProducer, Technology provider, water user, logistic operator
	ViewStatus	WaterStreamProducer, Technology provider, water user

4.1 Use case Diagram

The use case diagram in figure 5 represents the interactions between the platform and its primary actors (i.e., Water Stream Producer, Water user, Technology Provider, Logistic operator, Staff, Facility Manager).

Figure 5 - Use case Diagram

A detailed description for each functionality design is included. The description will provide the requirements for the implementation

1. addResource

This use case is for adding furniture record on the market place. After authentication or login using a token either by the facility manager, retailer, landlord, staff, and student can choose to add new furniture.

Primary Actors	👤 WaterStreamManager,
MOSCOW	Must
FURPS	Functional
Use Case Status	N/A
Implementation Status	N/A

Preconditions	Must be authenticated using a token or login
Post-conditions	The resource is added into the database and is now searchable
Author	N/A
Assumptions	N/A

2. AssignCollection

This use case is for assigning a logistic operation involving collection by the facility manager, water user, logistic operator. After authentication or login using a token, the primary actors can assign a logistic operator to deal with the product or resource if necessary

MOSCOW	Must
FURPS	Functional
Use Case Status	N/A
Implementation Status	N/A
Preconditions	Must be authenticated using a token or login
Post-conditions	Assigned collection
Author	N/A
Assumptions	View list of logistic operators registered

3. AssignDelivery

This use case is for assigning delivery of a resource, technology or product. After authentication or login using a token either by the facility manager or technology the delivery can be arranged with a registered Van and Man or a logistics operator

MOSCOW	Must
FURPS	Functional
Use Case Status	N/A
Implementation Status	Must be authenticated using a token or login
Preconditions	N/A
Post-conditions	N/A
Author	N/A
Assumptions	View a list of registered Van and Man and logistics operators

4. Authenticate

A platform user attempt to manage collection or manage resources thus the system will prompt the user for a username and password (i.e. request a token) or register a new account for Van and Man or logistic operator

MOSCOW	Must
FURPS	Functional
Use Case Status	N/A
Implementation Status	N/A
Preconditions	N/A
Post-conditions	The User is authenticated and the system displays manage resources or manage logistics page based on the user type
Author	N/A
Assumptions	

5. deleteResources

This use case describes the process of deleting furniture from the EcoBulk End-user platform.

MOSCOW	N/A
FURPS	Functional
Use Case Status	N/A
Implementation Status	N/A
Preconditions	The user must be authenticated or logged into the platform.
Post-conditions	The resource is deleted from the database and send a confirmation message/email.
Author	N/A
Assumptions	N/A

6. ManageLogistics

This use case provides the capability for technology provider, Water Stream producer, water user, and logistic operator to arrange collection or delivery. Also, users (primary actors) can assign delivery to a van and man or request other logistic operations.

MOSCOW	Must
FURPS	Functional
Use Case Status	N/A
Implementation Status	N/A
Preconditions	The user must be authenticated or register a new account.
Post-conditions	Display options to assign delivery, arrange collection, request other operations and view status.
Author	N/A
Assumptions	N/A

7. manageResource

This use case provides the capability for the water stream producer to manage their resources by adding, updating, editing and deleting furniture from the database.

MOSCOW	Must
FURPS	Functional
Use Case Status	N/A
Implementation Status	N/A
Preconditions	The user must be authenticated or register a new account.
Post-conditions	Display options to add, edit, update, and delete resources from the database.
Author	N/A
Assumptions	N/A

8. Register

A user of the system creates an account or register to manage their resources. This use case starts when a system user is not logged in to the system and attempt to manage furniture or manage a collection.

MOSCOW	Should
FURPS	Functional
Use Case Status	N/A
Implementation Status	N/A
Preconditions	The user must not be registered.
Post-conditions	The user entered successful information or valid token and is returned to the manage logisticsor manage resource page as a Logged In User.
Author	N/A
Assumptions	N/A

9. RequestResource

This use case will enable water Users to request resources via the market place

MOSCOW	Must
FURPS	Functional
Use Case Status	N/A
Implementation Status	N/A
Preconditions	The user must be authenticated or register new account
Post-conditions	Display available resources on the market place page and send request.
Author	N/A
Assumptions	N/A

10. UpdateResource

MOSCOW	N/A
FURPS	N/A
Use Case Status	N/A
Implementation Status	N/A
Preconditions	N/A
Post-conditions	N/A
Author	N/A
Assumptions	N/A

11. ViewResource

MOSCOW	N/A
FURPS	N/A
Use Case Status	N/A
Implementation Status	N/A
Preconditions	N/A
Post-conditions	N/A
Author	N/A
Assumptions	N/A

12. ViewStatus

MOSCOW	N/A
FURPS	N/A
Use Case Status	N/A
Implementation Status	N/A
Preconditions	N/A
Post-conditions	N/A
Author	N/A
Assumptions	N/A

13. ViewMarketPlace

Primary Actors	👤 WaterStreamProducer, 👤 Technology Provider, 👤 water User, 👤 Technoly provider
MOSCOW	N/A
FURPS	N/A
Use Case Status	N/A
Implementation Status	N/A
Preconditions	N/A
Post-conditions	N/A
Author	N/A
Assumptions	N/A

4.6 Activity Diagram

Activity Diagrams in Figure 9XXX describe how activities are coordinated to search for a resource which can be at different levels of abstraction. Typically, a user looking for alternatives for their water resource. Once an alternative to treat, circulate, or valorise the stream is found, the user may view the details and the actors involved. The technology provider, the user requesting the stream, or the water manager can review the request and confirm their interest. The user looking for alternatives along with the key actors will approve and arrange the logistics if necessary.

Figure 3 - Activity Diagram: Search Furniture

5. Conclusions

This document presents an approach to the identification of the roles, profiles and requirements for the development of Project O platform. The document includes the definition of the user roles, an in-depth study of the needs and requirements of the participants from the point of view of user stories, and the subsequent definition of product functions to solve the identified requirements.

The legacy of this platform after the end of the project will be considered in the next D7.3, where the possibility of developing it as a commercial product in order to constitute a spinoff asset will be analysed.

6. Appendix A

